

Advanced Affective and Cognitive Bases of Behaviour

Africa International University (AIU), Department of Psychology

PhD Clinical Psychology - Neuroanatomy and Neuroscience

THE ROLE OF THE PRE-FRONTAL CORTEX ON COGNITIVE ADAPTABILITY AND ITS IMPACT ON SCHIZOPHRENIA

A REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Author: P. Rupondo

Published 14 December 2025, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17928939

Copyright © 2025 Rupondo, P.

Africa International University, Department of Psychology, PhD Clinical Psychology, Clinical Neuropsychology, Neuroanatomy and Neuroscience, Nairobi, Kenya

KeyWords

Neurodevelopmental hypothesis, schizophrenia, pre-frontal cortex (PCF), fronto-parietal control network (FPCN), neuroanatomy, cognitive adaptability, cognitive flexibility

ABSTRACT

The prefrontal cortex (PFC) plays a central role in executive functions, including cognitive adaptability, which is crucial for managing schizophrenia-related cognitive impairments. This literature review explores the PFC's role in cognitive flexibility and adaptability, with a particular focus on how its dysfunction impacts individuals with schizophrenia. By reviewing global research on PFC neuroanatomy, cognitive adaptability, and schizophrenia, the paper synthesizes findings on neural mechanisms underpinning cognitive deficits in schizophrenia. Key themes include the foundational role of PFC in executive functioning, the significance of cognitive flexibility in daily life, and the implications of PFC dysfunction in schizophrenia symptomatology. The review also highlights theoretical frameworks such as Weinberger's neurodevelopmental hypothesis and Taylor's Cognitive Adaptation Theory, emphasizing the importance of early brain development and adaptive cognitive responses. While current research underscores the PFC's critical role, gaps remain regarding secondary factors like stress, motivation, and medication effects, prompting further investigation into targeted interventions to improve cognitive outcomes for schizophrenia patients.

1. INTRODUCTION

The prefrontal cortex (PFC) plays a significant role in cognitive functions including decision-making, planning, working memory, and cognitive adaptability. The dysfunction in the prefrontal cortex causes significant implications in varied psychological disorders, (Aleman, 2014, Sakurai and Gamo, 2019). Schizophrenia is a complex psychological disorder that is characterised by disturbances in thought processes, behaviour and emotions. Understanding the role of the prefrontal cortex in cognitive adaptability and its potential impact on schizophrenia is of significant importance for interpreting the underlying issues of this disorder for the development of effective psychological interventions. This literature review will explore the existing research on the role of the PFC in cognitive adaptability and its association with schizophrenia disorder. By identifying gaps and evaluating methodologies and synthesising key findings this review seeks to provide understanding of the topic and its implications in the understanding of schizophrenia.

The study employed a scoping review design to gather, appraise, and synthesize existing literature on the topic of this study. According to Munn, Peters, & Stern, et al (2018), scoping reviews involves mapping out existing literature and identifying key concepts, theories and gaps in alignment with the provided study topic. The reviewer employed a thematic analysis methodology for this review paper. Thematic analysis is a method that involves identifying patterns (themes) in data by systematically coding and organizing key ideas. It helps uncover underlying meanings and relationships, (Dawadi, 2020).

The reviewer employed a systematic search of electronic databases of literature in psychology and neuroscience to selected relevant literature. The search was expanded from peer review journals, review articles on the subject, meta-analysis, community communication journals, conference publications and empirical studies recent advancement publications in the field. Data was analysed using open coding to identify key ideas and patterns, grouping codes into refined themes that align with the current topic under review. Findings were interpreted and integrated into the study's literature review. The study aimed to examine research utilizing several approaches, such as neuroimaging techniques, cognitive assessments, and clinical evaluations, in order to derive significant insights into the correlation between PFC function, cognitive, and schizophrenia.

1.1 Objectives

This literature review aimed to investigate the existing research literature on the role of the prefrontal cortex (PFC) in cognitive adaptability, with the goal of providing light on the neural mechanisms underpinning this critical cognitive function. Secondly, the review attempted to investigate the complex association between PFC impairment and schizophrenia by analyzing relevant research and findings, with a focus on the influence of PFC dysfunction on cognitive flexibility and adaptive behaviours in people with this mental condition.

1.2 AN OVERVIEW OF KEY TERMINOLOGY

Prefrontal Cortex (PFC): The brain region responsible for executive functions like decision-making and working memory. Menon & D'Esposito, (2022).

Cognitive adaptability refers to the capacity to adjust one's cognitive processes and strategies in response to changing circumstances or environmental demands, (Bearden, and Shapero, 2019). *Cognitive flexibility* refers to the capacity to flexibly modify one's cognitive strategies, perspectives, and behaviours to effectively navigate different challenges, uncertainties, and environments, (MacPherson, et al, 2022, Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010)

Schizophrenia: A complex psychological disorder characterized by disturbances in thought processes, behaviours, and emotions, often involving hallucinations, delusions, and cognitive impairments. Schizophrenia is a neurodevelopmental disorder that affects youth in puberty and is manifested by disruption in cognition and emotion along with negative (ie, avolition, alogia, apathy, poor or non-existent social functioning, (American Psychiatric Association, 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The scope of this literature review investigated the relationship between the prefrontal cortex (PFC) and cognitive flexibility/adaptability, examining its profound impact on schizophrenia. Literature outlined in this research review paper emerged from diverse global locations, with studies being identified in Germany, United States of America, India and Spain covering Europe, Asia and the Americas. No studies emerged from Africa. While this reflects a collaborative effort to understand the complex relationship of neurobiology and cognitive functioning across different populations in relationship to schizophrenia, there is limited research on this subject.

Three key themes emerged within this scoping review. Firstly, that, the neuroanatomy of the PFC provides a foundational understanding of its structure and functions, particularly highlighting the subregions responsible for cognitive flexibility/adaptability. Secondly, the concept of cognitive flexibility and adaptability is elucidated, emphasizing their significance in daily life and cognitive functioning. Lastly, the schizophrenia and PFC dysfunction; clinical features of schizophrenia and associated cognitive deficits, including impairments in cognitive flexibility/adaptability. These themes underscore the relevance of investigating PFC dysfunction in the context of this psychological disorder. Through a thematic analysis of these themes, this literature review aimed to illuminate the neural mechanisms, neurobiological basis, and clinical implications of PFC functioning and cognitive flexibility/adaptability in schizophrenia, paving the way for targeted interventions and improved patient outcomes.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Weinberg's neurodevelopmental hypothesis for Schizophrenia

The key theoretical alignment of this review is embedded in Weinberger, (1996)'s neurodevelopmental hypothesis of schizophrenia. This hypothesis postulates that the disorder is connected to defects within brain development, predisposing individuals to a specific pattern of brain malfunction that occurs during early adulthood. This dysfunction, responsive to antidopaminergic drugs, manifests in symptoms characteristic of schizophrenia. The hypothesis is composed of three core components that is; *developmental neuropathology*, which suggests that abnormal brain development contributes to later symptoms; *brain malfunction*, which leads to diagnostically recognisable symptom responsive to antidopaminergic drugs; and finally; the *delayed clinical manifestation*, with the neurodevelopmental abnormality becoming clearer only after a significant postnatal delay. (Weinberger, 1996, Owen, O'Donovan, & Thapar, et al, 2011). Overall, the neurodevelopmental hypothesis underscores early brain developmental abnormalities as the foundation for schizophrenia's specific brain dysfunction patterns and symptomatic presentation, thereby connecting to this study topic on the role of the prefrontal cortex (PFC) in cognitive adaptability and its impact on schizophrenia.

Cognitive Adaptability Theory:

Taylor's (1983) Cognitive Adaptation Theory proposes that people respond to changing and threatening events by engaging in cognitively adaptive efforts. The theory underscores the significance of the role of cognitive flexibility in the relationship between cognitions and adaptive responses and functioning, suggesting that individuals may discover alternative responses serving the same function when specific cognitions are contradicted. In essence, the cognitive adaptation theory provides a distinctive perspective on human adaptation to changing events, portraying individuals as adaptable, self-protective, and adept at functioning effectively in the face of challenges. The theory highlights the importance of cognitive flexibility in shaping adaptive cognitive responses of individuals and their functioning. Essentially, the theory offers a unique perspective on cognitive processes and adaptation.

2.2 THE NEUROANATOMY OF THE PFC AND COGNITIVE ADAPTABILITY

The frontal lobes, particularly the prefrontal cortex (PFC), control the executive functions, that guide human behaviour through the coordination and integration of the basic mental or cognitive processes, (Ward, 2020, Segal and Elkana, 2023, Coutlee & Huettel, 2012). The prefrontal cortex (PFC) and its implications on cognitive adaptability and schizophrenia is central to this study. Understanding the anatomical and the functional organisation of the PFC system is significant in the exploration of the cognitive control mechanisms and their connectedness, (Weinberger, 1996, Menon et al, 2022, Segal et al, 2023). Figure 1 below by Racciah, Block, & Fox (2021)

shows the various section of the PFC.

Key: (sgACC) Subgenual ACC; (pgACC), pregenual ACC; (aMCC), anterior mid-cingulate cortex; (lOFC), lateral OFC; (mOFC), medial OFC; (lFPC), lateral frontopolar cortex; (mFPC), medial frontopolar cortex; (vFPC), ventral frontopolar cortex; (DMPFC), dorsomedial PFC.

Figure 1: *Raccach, Block, & Fox (2021) Anatomical parcellation of the human PFC. PFC regional delineation based on prior anatomic and neuroimaging studies. Prefrontal cortex: Dorsal System.*

This is crucial in unveiling the neural mechanisms that contribute to cognitive deficits in schizophrenia. Various studies and reviews have been conducted centring on the PFC. A paper by Menon et al, (2022) on the involvement of prefrontal cortical networks in cognitive regulation and executive function described the PFC as a very diverse brain structure with discrete anatomical units of neurochemical, microstructural and cytoarchitectonic aspects. These units work uniquely and interconnectedly (connection fingerprints) in the function of processing through specific patterns of the corticocortical and cortico-subcortical that separate units from other brain regions. Menon et al, (2022), further stated that denseness and interlinkage of the PFC play a critical role in functional aspects of adaptive and directed responses, (Weinberger, 1996, Segal et al, 2023).

Weinberger (1996)'s neurodevelopmental hypothesis for schizophrenia highlighted that the PFC is involved in cognitive adaptability through the functions of organisational flexibility on a vast scale on neural networks that integrate to facilitate cognitive control, that is; that salient, cinguloopercular, frontoparietal, dorsal and ventral attention systems. Figure 2 below by de Boer, Johnston, & Kerr, et al, (2020) illustrates the layout of the dorsal system outlining the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex.

Figure 2: de Boer, Johnston, & Kerr, et al, (2020): Endogenous Attention: Dorsolateral Prefrontal cortex: Dorsal System.

A paper by Selemon and Zecevic (2015) on schizophrenia and the two critical phases for prefrontal cortical development alluded on how research identified patterns and connectedness of the PFC using multimodal imaging and the computation methods. They indicated the distinct elements of the PFC's higher order and complex functions of cognitive functions. These include cognitive adaptability, emotional regulation, social cognition, decision making, attention, working memory, planning, flexibility and behavioural control functions, (Menon et al, 2022). According to Weinberger, (1996), PFC is a significant key element in the study of schizophrenia. Selemon et al, (2015)'s paper explored functional neuroimaging studies and how the PFC is often hyperactive in patients with schizophrenia. They indicated that this element is believed to contribute the cognitive deficits in the disorder. Overall, their paper stresses the need of investigating the prefrontal cortex and its functional abnormalities in order to better understand the neurobiological foundation of schizophrenia and its accompanying cognitive problems. The PFC is a multifunctional brain region that is crucial to various cognitive, emotional, and social functions, highlighting its importance in cognitive processes associated with schizophrenia.

2.3 THE CONCEPT OF COGNITIVE FLEXIBILITY AND ADAPTABILITY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN DAILY LIFE AND COGNITIVE FUNCTIONING FOR SCHIZOPHRENIA PATIENTS.

The PFC is neuroanatomically divided into multiple subregions, each with distinct functions. The ventromedial prefrontal cortex (VMPFC) is associated with decision-making and emotional regulation, while the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) is involved in working memory and cognitive control, (Menon et al, 2022, Segal et al, 2023). The ability to adapt cognitive strategies in response to changing environmental demands is known as *cognitive flexibility*. The anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) illustrated in figure 4 below by, Leisman and Melillo, (2013) is significant for observing and modifies cognitive control processes. Studies have revealed that cognitive versatility depends on the PFC, and more especially, the DLPFC. Damage or

malfunction of the PFC can lead to deficits in adaptive behaviour and cognitive flexibility. The PFC is involved in cognitively demanding tasks such as response inhibition and task switching, according to studies on functional MRI imaging. Because the PFC supports executive functions necessary for flexible and adaptive behaviour in response to shifting demands on cognition, its unique segments and linkages with various brain areas contribute to cognitive adaptability.

Figure 3: Leisman and Melillo, (2013), Cortico- limbic System

2.3.1 Frontal cingulate cortex and lateral prefrontal cortex decrease.

Making decisions, control of attention, emotion regulation, and error detection are all facilitated by the frontal cingulate cortex. Impulse control, inhibition, cognitive flexibility, and executive functions are all supported by the lateral prefrontal cortex, (Rolls, 2023). Figure 4 below illustrates the lateral PFC (Bush, 2011). A study by Wang, Hu, and Li (2022) in the *United States of America* used task-oriented whole-brain functional connections to investigate cognitive flexibility problems in schizophrenia. Their results demonstrated that when schizophrenia patients were asked to complete activities demanding cognitive flexibility, there was a decrease in the frontal cingulate cortex and lateral prefrontal cortex of the brain. They emphasized task modulated connection changes between massive neural networks and emphasized schizophrenia as a condition characterized by functional dysconnectivity in the area of the prefrontal cortex. This

study investigated task-related connection alterations during cognitive tasks, in contrast to earlier research that concentrated on resting-state connectivity. These findings highlight the critical role the prefrontal cortex plays in cognitive deficiencies in people with schizophrenia and the necessity of understanding these abnormalities in light of the population's reduced cognitive flexibility.

Another study on negative symptoms of schizophrenia as prefrontal brain dysfunction assessment utilizing a task assessing goal neglect was conducted in *Spain* by Fuentes-Claramonte, Pomarol-Clotet, Salvador, et al. (2022). The study found a correlation between lower prefrontal cortex reactivity and negative symptoms of schizophrenia. The frontal concept of negative symptoms was supported by the fact that patients with high negative symptoms (HNS) and absent negative symptoms (ANS) patients and healthy controls showed less activation in important prefrontal areas. This study demonstrates a connection between negative symptoms in schizophrenia and decreased activation of the prefrontal cortex, particularly in the left anterior frontal lobe. This was demonstrated using a test measuring goal neglect, supporting the frontal hypothesis that prefrontal dysfunction contributes to these symptoms. The left parietal cortex showed unexpectedly low activation in the study, indicating that it is involved in cognitive regulation.

2.3.2 The Fronto-Parietal Control Network (FPCN): Detecting rule switches and inhibiting drifts efficiently in the pre-frontal cortex.

Adaptive behaviour and adaptable decision-making depend on the prefrontal cortex's ability to effectively detect rule shifts and inhibit drifts. To retain attention and accomplish intended results, this function entails the ability to detect changes in task rules or goals and suppress irrelevant information or distractions, (Deck, Kelkar and Erickson, et al, 2023). Rodgers, & DeWeese, (2014) on their simulation experiment on neural correlates associated with task switching in the PFC and the primary auditory cortex found that rodents can select to respond to one task or activity above many others taking place at the same time and can easily switch to another effortlessly.

Rodents were trained to respond to two sounds simultaneously on speakers. Each trial started with you holding their nose in the centre port, triggering the presentation of one of four task signal stimulus pairs: Left + High, Right +High, Left + Low, or Right + Low. The rodents were required to respond to the task stimuli but also had an option to choose to 'go left,' or 'go right' or 'no-go' cues based on the sounds giving them options to switch between task stimuli.

Figure 5: Neural Correlates of Task Switching: Auditory stimulus selection (Rodgers, & DeWeese, 2014)

They concluded the same principle for human beings. This makes shows that healthy humans and animals can detect rule switches and select and switch tasks. In a study in *Germany*, Standke, Trempler and Dannlowski et al, (2021), found that patients with schizophrenia spectrum disorders, compared to healthy controls, had difficulty detecting rule switches and inhibiting drifts efficiently. This was linked to a weaker ability to discriminate between switches and drifts, correlated with reduced striatal response indicating impaired prediction error processing. Patients also showed reduced activity in key brain regions during behavioural adaptation after errors. These results suggest significant impairments in cognitive flexibility and stability among individuals with schizophrenia spectrum disorders. The findings of the study imply that problems in identifying rule changes and suppressing irrelevant information are associated with decreased cognitive stability and flexibility in schizophrenia. Improved prediction analysis includes reduced switch-drift discrimination, adaptation, error processing, focus, decision-making, task switching, and behavioural adjustments are further symptoms of these cognitive deficits that impact daily functioning at work, social interactions, and overall quality of life.

Mittal, Mehta, and Solanki, et al, (2013) conducted a study in *India*, and examined cognitive flexibility in young people with both first episode and multi-episode schizophrenia and found that both groups had significantly less cognitive flexibility than the control group. Overall impairments were similar, despite one test where first episode patients did slightly better. Additionally, negative symptoms and psy-

chopathology scores were higher in first episode patients. These findings corroborate the neurodevelopmental foundation of schizophrenia and point to the promise of cognitive rehabilitation therapy by indicating that cognitive flexibility deficiencies are inherent to the disorder.

Moritz, Silverstein, and Beblo, et al (2021), suggested that schizophrenia patients perform badly on neuropsychological tasks. According to their *German* study, neurocognitive impairment in schizophrenia may not only be caused by the illness itself, but also by positive symptoms, stress, motivation, effort, and drug side effects. According to Moritz, et al, (2021)'s study, neurocognitive impairment in schizophrenia may not only be caused by the illness itself, but also by beneficial symptoms such as stress, exertion, motivation, and pharmaceutical side effects. Ignoring these factors could lead to an overestimation of the degree of impairment solely related to schizophrenia. Beyond cognitive rehabilitation, an improved awareness of these secondary variables may result in more successful treatments.

4. INTERPRETATION OF EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

Below is a summary of empirical findings from this literature review.

4.1 Table 1: Interpretation of Empirical Findings: Thematic Analysis

8

Key Words: PFC: Pre-frontal Cortex; Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DPCA); Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC), Frontal Pole; Orbitofrontal Cortex (OFC); Frontal pole (FP)

Location	Researchers	Key Theme	Findings	Functions of PFC	Impact of PFC impairment on Schizophrenia
Germany	Standke, Trempler, Dannlowski, et al (2021)	PFC Dysfunction in Schizophrenia	Individuals with schizophrenia spectrum disorders experienced difficulties in the Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DPCA), the Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC), the Frontal Pole, and the Orbitofrontal Cortex (OFC) of the PFC in terms of recognizing and detecting rule shifts as well as effectively regulating drifts.	<i>Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DLPFC):</i> Contributes to task switching, working memory, and cognitive regulation. <i>The Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC)</i> oversees cognitive flexibility, conflict monitoring, and error detection. <i>Frontal Pole:</i> Linked to higher order cognitive processes including planning and decision-making. <i>The orbitofrontal cortex (OFC)</i> is a brain region that controls emotions and makes decisions.	This highlights PFC impairment and suggests a reduction in cognitive flexibility and stability in schizophrenia spectrum illnesses. DLPFC and OFC dysfunction can make it harder to recognize rule alterations and block out irrelevant information. ACC may make it more difficult to modify behaviour in response to shifting guidelines or objectives. Ineffectiveness in this domain may affect the capacity to recognize modifications in task rules.
Germany	Menon et al. (2022)	Neuroanatomy of the PFC	The PFC subregions are diverse and interrelated; higher order and complex processes, as well as the salient, cinguloopercular, frontoparietal, dorsal, and ventral attention systems, are essential for cognitive flexibility.	<i>Higher order and complex functions:</i> Cognitive adaptability, emotional regulation, social cognition, decision-making, attention, working memory, planning, flexibility, and behavioral control functions. <i>Salient, Cinguloopercular, Frontoparietal, Dorsal, and Ventral Attention Systems:</i> cognitive adaptability, cognitive control, emotional regulation, social cognition, decision-making, attention, working memory, planning, flexibility, and behavioral control functions. They are crucial for integrating neural networks and facilitating cognitive control and adaptability in response to various cognitive, emotional, and social demands.	PFC impairment is linked to negative feelings, decreased cognitive flexibility, and cognitive deficiencies in patients with schizophrenia. The hyperactivity of the PFC in schizophrenia reflects impairment in areas related to emotional control and cognitive flexibility, which in turn leads to cognitive deficiencies.
USA	Wang, Hu, Li (2022)	Cognitive Flexibility Problems in Schizophrenia	Patients with schizophrenia had reduced activity in the lateral prefrontal cortex and	<i>Frontal Cingulate Cortex:</i> Facilitates decision-making, attention control, emotion regulation, and error detection. <i>Lateral</i>	Decreased activation in PFC regions related to cognitive flexibility problems in schizophrenia in relations to the stated functions.

Location	Researchers	Key Theme	Findings	Functions of PFC	Impact of PFC impairment on Schizophrenia
			frontal cingulate cortex when performing activities that required cognitive flexibility.	<i>Prefrontal Cortex:</i> Supports impulse control, inhibition, cognitive flexibility, and executive functions. Decreased activation in frontal cingulate cortex and lateral prefrontal cortex; schizophrenia patients showed decreased activation in these areas during activities demanding cognitive flexibility, indicating dysfunction.	
<i>Spain</i>	Fuentes-Claramonte, Pomarol-Clotet, Salvador, et al (2022)	Prefrontal Brain Dysfunction in Schizophrenia	The association between negative symptoms in schizophrenia and reduced prefrontal cortex reactivity suggests that the severity of symptoms and PFC dysfunction are related.	The <i>DLPFC</i> is commonly implicated in cognitive control, working memory, and executive functions. <i>ACC</i> , The ACC is involved in emotion regulation, error detection, and cognitive flexibility. <i>Orbitofrontal Cortex (OFC):</i> The OFC plays a role in decision-making, reward processing, and emotional regulation. <i>Frontal Pole:</i> Associated with higher-order cognitive functions and decision-making.	Negative symptoms and PFC impairment are correlated, pointing to a potential role for the brain region in the expression of schizophrenia symptoms. Negative symptoms and decreased activation seen in the study may be related to dysfunction in the DPCA and OFC. Negative symptoms and prefrontal dysfunction may also be associated with alterations in ACC activity. Reduced activity in prefrontal areas and negative symptoms could be caused by dysfunction in the frontal pole.
<i>India</i>	Mittal, Mehta, Solanki, et al (2013)	Cognitive Adaptability in Schizophrenia	Schizophrenia patients with first episode and those with several episodes showed considerably reduced cognitive flexibility when compared to controls. According to the study, people with schizophrenia had trouble performing cognitively demanding activities including focusing attention on various stimuli at once or changing their answers in reaction to new information.	The ACC plays a role in error detection, conflict monitoring, and cognitive flexibility. <i>Frontal Pole:</i> Associated with higher-order cognitive functions	Cognitive flexibility deficiencies as inherent to schizophrenia, impacting patient functioning. They are difficulties in tasks requiring cognitive flexibility, such as shifting attention between different stimuli or adjusting responses based on new information
<i>Germany</i>	Moritz, Silverstein, Beblo, et	Neurocognitive Deficits in Schizo-	Neurocognitive impairment in schizophrenia may be	<i>DLPFC:</i> The DLPFC plays a crucial role in cognitive control, working memory, and	Influence of secondary factors on neurocognitive impairment in schizophrenia, suggesting

	al (2021)	phrenia	impacted by several variables, including motivation, stress, and adverse drug reactions.	executive functions. ACC is involved in error detection, conflict monitoring, and emotional regulation. FP associated with higher-order cognitive functions such as decision-making, social cognition, and emotional regulation The OFC plays a role in decision-making, reward processing, and emotional regulation.	a multifactorial etiology for cognitive deficits. DLPFC: Dysfunction in this area can lead to deficits in various cognitive processes, including attention, planning, and problem-solving. ACC activation is related to difficulties in cognitive control and emotional processing observed in schizophrenia. FP impairments in cognitive flexibility and behavioral control. OFC activation is associated with cognitive deficits and emotional dysregulation in schizophrenia.
--	-----------	---------	--	---	--

This table gives an overview of the studies that were carried out in various locations, the researchers who were involved, the year the work was published, the main themes that were investigated, the specific findings about PFC dysfunction and cognitive flexibility in schizophrenia, and the way in which these findings are directly related to our understanding of the disorder schizophrenia.

The literature review included studies from four global locations as follows; Germany; Standke, Trempler, Dannowski et al. (2021) and Menon et al, (2022), United States of America; Wang, Hu, Li (2022), India: Mittal, Mehta, Solanki et al. (2013) and Spain; Fuentes-Claramonte, Pomarol-Clotet, Salvador et al. (2022). The key themes that emerged were the neuroanatomy of PFC with studies that emphasized the PFC's diverse functions and anatomical complexity. Secondly the cognitive flexibility or adaptability with studies emphasising the crucial for daily functioning, showing the PFC playing as a key system. Lastly, schizophrenia and PFC dysfunction where studies linked cognitive deficits in schizophrenia to various PFC abnormalities. Findings also included the work of theorists reviewed in relationship to this study.

4.2 Theoretical Findings

Findings from a theoretical framework point of view emerged in *Weinberger's Neurodevelopmental Hypothesis* (1996) which alluded and emphasised on the early brain developmental abnormalities in schizophrenia patients with a specific emphasis on the PFC dysfunction. Taylor's Cognitive Adaptation Theory (1993) focused on individuals' cognitive adaptability aligned to changing events, thus emphasising the importance of cognitive flexibility. Weinberger's Neurodevelopmental Hypothesis emphasizes how early brain development disorders, namely PFC problems, provide the groundwork for schizophrenia. Cognitive adaptability is crucial for people to be able to adjust to shifting circumstances, as highlighted by Taylor's Cognitive Adaptation Theory.

4.3 Empirical Findings

The prefrontal cortex (PFC) plays a significant role in executive functions, cognitive control, emotional regulation, and adaptive responses. Studies explored the relationship between PFC functioning and cognitive adaptability in schizophrenia patients across different countries. In Germany, Standke et al. (2021) found impaired cognitive flexibility in schizophrenia patients, which was associated with a reduced striatal response, highlighting neural correlates of cognitive deficits. Similarly, in the United States, Wang et al. (2022) observed decreased PFC activation during tasks requiring cognitive flexibility in schizophrenia, indicating functional abnormalities. In India, Mittal et al. (2013) found that patients with schizophrenia exhibited reduced cognitive flexibility, indicating that neurodevelopmental factors may be at play in the cognitive impairments. The clinical significance of PFC dysfunction in symptom severity was highlighted by Fuentes-Claramonte et al. (2022) in Spain, who connected decreased PFC activation to negative symptoms of schizophrenia. Collectively, these results highlight the complex interplay of PFC functioning, cognitive flexibility, and pathology associated with schizophrenia in a variety of populations.

4.4 Comparative Analysis of Studies

4.4.1 *Similar Findings:*

All studies that emerged in this literature review found deficits in cognitive flexibility or adaptability in schizophrenia patients either compared to controls or not. The PFC was found to be consistently and significantly related to cognitive deficits and symptomatology consistent with the schizophrenia spectrum across all studies.

4.4.2 **Differences – Methodology**

Studies that emerged in this literature review employed a variation on methodologies to uncover the role of the PFC and its impact on cognitive adaptability and schizophrenia. The study by Standke et al. (2021) in Germany employed the task-oriented methodology to assess cognitive flexibility / adaptability in schizophrenia patients, focusing on neural correlates such as the reduced striatal response. Wang et al. (2022) in the United States applied the functional MRI imaging to observe the rate of decreased PFC activation during tasks requiring cognitive flexibility in schizophrenia, emphasizing neural correlates. On the other hand, Mittal et al. (2013) in India administered cognitive assessments in order to explore the lower cognitive flexibility / adaptability in schizophrenia patients which showed neurodevelopmental foundational elements of schizophrenia. In Spain Fuentes-Claramonte et al. (2022) employed brain imaging techniques and methodologies to connect negative symptoms of schizophrenia to the decreased PFC activation, in this case, highlighting clinical symptomatology.

Studies conducted by both Standke et al. (2021) and Wang et al. (2022), placed more attention on neural correlates such as reduced striatal response and decreased the PFC activation, respectively, as a mechanism of understanding cognitive adaptability deficits in schizophrenia. Conversely, both Mittal et al. (2013) and Fuentes-Claramonte et al. (2022) highlighted potential significant factors beyond the issues of cognitive adaptability deficits in schizophrenia', such as neurodevelopmental foundations, stress and motivation as significant contributing factors to cognitive impairments in schizophrenia patients. These varied accents provide a diverse view of the multi-dimensional factors influencing cognitive adaptability in the context of schizophrenia disorder.

4. IMPLICATION OF FINDINGS AND GAPS

The evaluation of the research highlights important implications and knowledge gaps about the connection between schizophrenia, cognitive flexibility, and the prefrontal cortex (PFC). The results support Weinberger's neurodevelopmental theory by highlighting the fundamental anomalies in early brain development that underlie the distinct brain dysfunction patterns associated with schizophrenia. The review emphasizes the significance of examining PFC anomalies to gain a better understanding of schizophrenia by highlighting the crucial function of the PFC in cognitive adaptation and its impact on the condition. Additionally, it highlights the significance of cognitive adaptation and flexibility in day-to-day functioning and cognitive functioning for individuals with schizophrenia, suggesting possible areas for focused therapy. Nevertheless, knowledge of the roles played by extraneous variables such as stress, motivation, and medication side effects in neurocognitive impairment in schizophrenia remains notably incomplete. Further-

more, although studies on the functional properties of brain regions such as the PFC have been conducted, more investigation is required to determine the precise neural mechanisms and connection patterns that underlie cognitive abnormalities in schizophrenia. By filling in these gaps and creating more potent interventions that take secondary characteristics into account, we may be able to manage cognitive deficiencies associated with schizophrenia more comprehensively and with better results for patients.

The literature review concludes by highlighting the prefrontal cortex's (PFC) crucial function in cognitive adaptation and its consequences for schizophrenia. The findings underline the necessity for focused interventions to address cognitive deficiencies in schizophrenia and corroborate Weinberger's neurodevelopmental hypothesis. Nevertheless, there are still unanswered questions about the precise brain mechanisms behind these abnormalities as well as the roles of secondary factors. To improve outcomes for people with schizophrenia and create more potent treatments, future research should concentrate on closing these gaps.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the prefrontal cortex (PFC) plays a vital role in cognitive adaptability and flexibility, functions that are significantly impaired in individuals with schizophrenia. This review highlights the intricate relationship between PFC dysfunction and the cognitive deficits observed in schizophrenia, emphasizing the region's involvement in executive functions such as decision-making, emotional regulation, and adaptive behavior. Through the analysis of global studies, it becomes evident that PFC abnormalities are strongly linked to cognitive impairments in schizophrenia, affecting patients' ability to navigate complex cognitive tasks and daily challenges.

The review also underscores the relevance of theoretical frameworks like Weinberger's neurodevelopmental hypothesis, which emphasizes early brain development abnormalities as foundational to schizophrenia's manifestation. Moreover, Taylor's Cognitive Adaptation Theory highlights the role of cognitive flexibility in adapting to changing environments, which is crucial for individuals with schizophrenia.

Despite significant insights into the PFC's role, there remain gaps in understanding how external factors such as stress, motivation, and medication influence cognitive impairments in schizophrenia. Addressing these gaps could lead to more effective, targeted interventions. Future research should focus on exploring these secondary variables and developing therapies that enhance cognitive adaptability in schizophrenia, thereby improving patient outcomes and quality of life.

Acknowledgment

The authors wish to thank Africa International University, Department of Psychology (AIU), faculty:

Prof. N. Ireri, Dr S.O Ojuade, Dr P. Ochieng

REFERENCES

- American Psychiatric Association. (2022). Bipolar and related Disorders. In *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed., text rev.).
- Aleman, A. (2014). Neurocognitive Basis of Schizophrenia: Information Processing Abnormalities and Clues for Treatment. *Advances in Neuroscience*, (104920), 1-15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/104920>
- Bearden, C. E., & Shapero, B. G. (2019). Social Cognition and Cognitive Flexibility in Bipolar Disorder. In D. E. Carlston (Ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Social Cognition* (pp. 335-374). Oxford University Press
- Bush, G. (2011). Cingulate, frontal, and parietal cortical dysfunction in attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Biological Psychiatry*, 69, 1160-1167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2011.01.022>
- Coutlee, C. G., & Huettel, S. A. (2012). The functional neuroanatomy of decision making: Prefrontal control of thought and action. *Brain Research*, 1428, 3-12.
- de Boer, D. M. L., Johnston, P. J., Kerr, G., Meinzer, M., & Cleeremans, A. (2020). A causal role for the right angular gyrus in self-location mediated perspective taking. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 19229. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-76235-7>
- Deck, B. L., Kelkar, A., Erickson, B., Erani, F., McConathey, E., Sacchetti, D., Faseyitan, O., Hamilton, R., & Medaglia, J. D. (2023). Individual-level functional connectivity predicts cognitive control efficiency. *Neuro-Image*, 283, 120386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2023.120386>
- Fuentes-Claramonte, P., Pomarol-Clotet, E., Salvador, R., McKenna, P., Ramiro, N., Torres, L., Argila-Plaza, I., Salgado-Pineda, P., Soler-Duncan, J., Panicalli, E., Boix, E., Tristany, J., Munuera, J., Sarró, S., Albacete, A., Bosque, C., Vidal, F., Salvador Sarró, S., Santo-Angles, A., Lechon, M., Guardiola-Ripoll, M., Almodovar-Paya, C., Bernado, M., & García-León, A. (2022). Reduced prefrontal activation as a brain functional correlate of negative symptoms in schizophrenia: A fMRI study using the Computerized Multiple Elements Test. *Neuro-Image Clinical*, 35, 103119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2022.103119>
- Leisman, G., & Melillo, R. (2013). The Development of the Frontal Lobes in Infancy and Childhood: Asymmetry and the Nature of Temperament and Affect. In N. E. Alessi (Ed.), *Frontal Lobe: Anatomy, Functions and Injuries* (pp. 23-56). Nova Science Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4461.7041>
- Menon, V., & D'Esposito, M. (2022). Large-scale brain networks in cognition: emerging methods and principles. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 47(1), 90-103.
- Mittal, P. K., Mehta, S., Solanki, R. K., & Swami, M. K. (2013). A comparative study of cognitive flexibility among first episode and multi-episode young schizophrenia patients. *German Journal of Psychiatry*, 16(1), ISSN 1433-1055.
- Moritz, S., Silverstein, S. M., Beblo, T., Özaslan, Z., Zink, M., & Gallinat, J. (2021). Much of the neurocognitive impairment in

schizophrenia is due to factors other than schizophrenia itself: Implications for research and treatment. *Schizophrenia Bulletin Open*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schizbullopen/sgaa034>

- Munn, Z., Peters, M. D. J., Stern, C., Tufanaru, C., McArthur, A., & Aromataris, E. (2018). Systematic review or scoping review? Guidance for authors when choosing between a systematic or scoping review approach. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1), 143. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-018-0611-x>
- Owen, M. J., O'Donovan, M. C., Thapar, A., & Craddock, N. (2011). Neurodevelopmental hypothesis of schizophrenia. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 198(3), 173–175. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.110.084384>
- Raccah, O., Block, N., & Fox, K. C. R. (2021). Does the Prefrontal Cortex Play an Essential Role in Consciousness? Insights from Intracranial Electrical Stimulation of the Human Brain. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 41(10), 2076-2087. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1141-20.2020>
- Rodgers, C. C., & DeWeese, M. R. (2014). Neural correlates of task switching in prefrontal cortex and primary auditory cortex in a novel stimulus selection task for rodents. *Neuron*, 82(5), 1157-1170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2014.04.031>
- Rolls, E. T. (2023). The cingulate cortex. In E. T. Rolls (Ed.), *Brain Computations and Connectivity* (pp. 564-595). DOI:10.1093/oso/9780198887911.003.0012
- Segal, O., & Elkana, O. (2023). The ventrolateral prefrontal cortex is part of the modular working memory system: A functional neuroanatomical perspective. *Frontiers in Neuroanatomy*, 17, 1076095. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnana.2023.1076095>
- Standke, I., Trempler, I., Dannlowski, U., Schubotz, R. I., & Lencer, R. (2021). Cerebral and behavioral signs of impaired cognitive flexibility and stability in schizophrenia spectrum disorders. *Neuro-Image Clinical*, 32, 102855. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2021.102855>
- Wang, Y., Hu, X., & Li, Y. (2022). Investigating cognitive flexibility deficit in schizophrenia using task-based whole-brain functional connectivity. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13, 1069036. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2022.1069036>
- Weinberger, D. R. (1996). Symposium on the plausibility of "The neurodevelopmental hypothesis" of schizophrenia. *Neuro-psychopharmacology*, 14(Suppl), 1S-11S.